

A review of the outbreak of *Leptospira* in humans and companion animals (dogs, cats and rodents) in Iran

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Abstract

Leptospirosis is a common bacterial disease between humans and animals, and therefore the control and prevention of this disease is very important from the point of view of public health. In this article, referring to reliable researches and reports conducted in the country, which were obtained by searching keywords such as *Leptospira*, Iran, dog, human in search engines such as Google Scholar and PubMed, to investigate the prevalence of the causative agent. This disease has been studied in dogs, cats, rodents and humans. By knowing the presence and prevalence of this factor in different regions of the country, necessary measures can be taken to effectively control and prevent this disease. The obtained results indicate the prevalence of this factor between 5.4% and 71% in the dog population, the prevalence between 4.9% and 27.03% in the cat population, and the prevalence between 3.3% and 21.73% in the rodent population. And the prevalence is between 1.1% and 61.6% in humans.

Key words: *Leptospira*, human, dog, cat, rodent, Iran